

Global Power Dynamics And Pakistan's Foreign Policy

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Abstract

There is nothing permanent and not will be in this world. Same is the case with countries' foreign policies and their power status. It keeps on changing. History witnessed dearest friends becoming worst enemies. Worst enemies becoming best friends. Pakistan had failed the FATF because FATF wanted to secure place in Pakistan's foreign policy. UK has changed its travel advisory towards Pakistan followed by United States of America. Pakistan had made serious efforts to create soft image in the eyes of the world. Terrorism causes problems for Pakistan as it tarnished respectful image of Pakistan, but it has been controlled. It is Pakistan's economy that compels it not to strike a balanced international approach in major dynamics of global power. To avoid problems in Pakistan foreign policy, Pakistan has adopted harsh and aggressive measures in its economic sphere to boost up its economic strength. For this purpose, it signed the agreement of CPEC with China to avail Chinese markets. Its main purpose was to meet unemployment, energy shortage and infrastructure in Pakistan.

Introduction

There is nothing permanent and not will be in this world. Same is the case with countries' foreign policies and their power status. It keeps on changing. History witnessed dearest friends becoming worst enemies. Worst enemies becoming best friends. The recent power jostle and fall are altering the factors that determine world power. General productivity growth was made between earthly civilizations or peoples, wars and battles (M. K. Khan & Wei, 2016). After World War II, the United States and Britain did not wage a battle for power to increase their stature. Due to the British being so tired, they ran out of energy to continue the hostilities and save electricity. No one can hold the power status to itself. The US was thought to remain the only superpower but all changed after 2000s. The global energy structure is changing, and new norms and values are being organized to take into account the new interests. Dominant participants are those who can take advantage of the new situation. However, the September 11 terrorist attacks and the increasing popularity of countries in emerging markets have both slowed down recently.

As in the past, the rise of new political players such as Russia and China, as well as many other growing economies, would create an alliance to fight the United States. Because of their capacities, developing regional powers are attempting to strengthen their sovereignty in global affairs. The current age of transition and power balance demonstrates the struggle of developing state trends to establish their position in the globe.

GLOBAL POWER DYNAMICS

World Power Structure: A Theoretical Framework

One of the defining trademarks that we analyze in international relations is the extent and intricacy of interconnection. We observe from history that the US enjoyed the superpower title for a very long time as a single world player. But with time passage and arrogance of the US regimes, there was its downfall, and many other countries took advantage of it. Russia, China, Turkey and Germany were among those countries. The Great Britain had survived the existing international system for nearly two hundred years because of their strong growing economy. Long-term strategic aims have been met with American hegemony. Since the early 1940s, the United States has attempted to establish a unipolar power structure in the international system.

The United States wishes to maintain regional stability, saying that it is important to protect an international order controlled by the United States by replacing anarchy with a hierarchy in these regions.

The Single Superpower Era

Prior to 1990, the world was split into two camps: superpowers and non-superpowers. After World War II, the British Empire began to decline and the United States became a superpower in space. For philosophical reasons, the two have been engaged in a war of words (a non-violent form of warfare) for some time now. The world was extremely unstable, with the continual threat of nuclear war. When Pakistan was accepted, it already had a private corporation that was a US partner. The Soviet Union decayed and became the United States Federation in 1989. The power structure of Russia and the world has transformed to a unipolar world dominated by the United States (KARATAŞ, 2021). It did, however, lose some international scholars and professionals, the US Unipolar Seconds. The globe has entered a new period of strong global competitiveness.

21st Century and The Fall of The Only Superpower

Since 2000 worldwide organizations made their extrapolation of superpower tag would not remain to just the US but many other countries will either share it or fight for it. China and Russia will be among these. Take 1978 as an example: 9.4 per cent gross domestic product of makes China fastest growing regional and world economy. Furthermore, its international commerce was worth \$20.6 billion. China has few mobile telecommunications services in the late twentieth century. There are already over 300 million mobile phone customers worldwide, and over 100 million individuals have internet access. China is introducing its domestic consumer sector in order to establish a robust and well-developed domestic market. China's billionaires' contracts and development of non-fossil fuels under the 12th five-year plan have the future planning of becoming world leader. More than half of China's economy is built on private enterprise, which contributes to the country's economic stability. Russian raise was seen in early 2000s. First, Clinton's knob fingers with Medvedev pressed the retune button, and the US moved quickly for NATO expansion on Russia's eastern boundaries. Second, the color revolutions and the Georgia War alienated Russia from the international club and strengthened the influence of pro-Russian strongman Putin. Under Yeltsin, the Russian per capita GDP was \$1000, and it reached \$9000 under Putin's leadership in 2012. Between 2000 and 2008, overall output climbed by 67 percent, stock market capitalization increased by 22 times, and international trade turnover increased by five times. Russian re-emergence may be explored through actions such as becoming an energy powerhouse and restoring domestic stability by ending poor leadership, balancing against the West and preserving its influence over newly independent states such as Belarus and Ukraine, among others. Putin's policies laid the groundwork for Russia's re-emergence through fast economic development, which has been the mainstay of the country's economic restoration (Victoria, 2006).

World Countries Struggling For Dominance

Presently, there are 7 Nuclear Powers in the world. Here we are going to discuss the geopolitical position of each country and how they can become a superpower.

Russia:

Irrespective of Russia's presence in various high profile flash points, Russia is still in a decline phase owing to numerous factors. Political power of Russia is a long haul from what was its position during the height of Soviet

Union. At present, Russia has multiple issues to be tackled upon. Recently the president of Russia is Vladimir Putin. Objective policies driven by Putin are based on rebuilding Russia's international stand and reinforce the country's power status. Moreover, President Putin has sought cultivation of relations with China without falling into the orbit of Beijing. Meanwhile, internal, and external politics of Russia have somehow succeeded, its attempt of modernizing and diversifying the economy of country has a dire need to be viewed as a setback. An average annual growth rate of Russia's economy is merely 1% on account of diminished diversification and the consequences posed by Russia's activity in Ukraine which resulted in international sanctions. Furthermore, the demographic situation of country compromised the attempts of Russia (Dyner, 2012). In order to be a

superpower, Russia needs to pave a way for reversing its demographic decline, in addition to, steps taken for modernizing its economy.

United States of America:

USA is being characterized as a superpower. However, the exposure of emerging economies has hindered its importance. United States of America (USA) was the only country to rise up after World War II (WWII) with distinctive economic and military structure. Hence, USA enjoyed a unique place while bringing peace among countries. The consequence was Global Financial System whose primary objective was to coordinate the global system and avoid depression. United Nations (UN) was established to maintain the post power peace. US formed its first permanent, major and non-war time alliance, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) while competing with Soviet Union (KARATAŞ, 2021). Additionally, it also led the foundation and development of US military and political position resulting in peace building in places such as Vietnam and Afghanistan and collaboration with Saudi Arabia and South Korea.

China:

China is appearing as a new superpower on the world's map, and it is about to put back the US from global power system. This country is rising powerfully from the global economic crisis flourishing because of Covid-19 pandemic and also the ally-alienating policies of the US president Trump within NATO have greatly pushed this matter. Undoubtedly, China has already become an economic global powerhouse and it will transcend US as the world's biggest economy most probably by 2028. Though China is falling behind, but it is on its way to surpass US in its military position by developing various secretive military weapons. We can say that there is no doubt over China gaining the economic and military strength just like US whether sooner or later. The question arises here is that can a Communist party which China led ever be as direful and complete the superpower as US has been for last 8 decades? Similar to Soviet Union in the old days, China is handling several challenges

regarding geopolitics and culture prior to surpassing US as a global power. Unlike US, China cannot acquire the same respect and acceptance as expected despite its economic and military power beats the US. This is due to the fact that a Democratic US will enjoy cultural, political, and ideological superiority than a Communist China forever(Almotairi, 2021).

France:

France was a superpower as The Empire of French in mid-19th century. Now analysts describe it best for regional strength. A month ago, before its remarkable conquest, the Emanuel Macron had every reason to be optimistic, he revealed “the beginning of new momentum” in France. “I want France to become a startup nation, a nation which not only works for the startups but also the nation which thinks and moves like startup”. France dreams of designing itself like a “start-up” power that is quick off the mark, resilient, innovative, and capable of playing great power politics while influencing multi-literalism for the interest of Europe and France(White & Heath, 2017). The strike attempts on Syria due to Syria’s use of chemical weapons accompanying the US and UK illustrate France’s readiness to utilize power to sustain international norms. Relocating of France takes place as the post-cold war international order is disintegrating. The USA has flourished as unreliable. EU, afflict with internal discord, has yet to get weight on the world scene. Russia, Revisionist power, brings about uncertainty among allies and weakens international security architecture. France will itself keep contending with internal centrifugal force like populism and nationalists etc. Then it will be able to emerge like a superpower.

The Great Britain

British Empire has ruled the world for over a century and no such example of an empire so great is found in the history. Its establishment started from British colonization in North America and then in Asia, Pacific, and Africa. Britain's military and economic power and cultural influence facilitated its takeover of major territories like the subcontinent, it dominated the world trade and influenced the economies of Asia and Latin America.

- The British empire of almost two-third of World began to crumble with the events that took place in 20th century. Due to World War one and two, the military and financial resources suffered greatly, and the underpinnings of British Empire were shaken to their core. With successive decolonization of major territories, including India, the spread of British Empire on most of the land area became limited. The underlying factors were the following: challenges of its dominance by countries like America and Germany and the world wars which followed, the freedom struggle by the people of occupied territories like India, the opposition of British colonization by Russia and America during the Cold war, and finally the shock to Britain’s financial resources after World wars. All of this resulted in complete decolonization by 1980's(Potter, 2007).
- Despite the glorious history of rule and dominance over the world, Britain seems to have stayed in decline in terms of being a global power till this day. The decline is evident from Britain's little influence on international affairs and its weak diplomatic capabilities. And the future of Britain as a superpower is bleak with no prospects of dominance over world. From the 20th century the dominance has been in the hands of Russia and America, China being the prospective superpower with the second largest economy expected to surpass America in the terms of military power also.

India

India, the world’s most populous democracy with one of world's biggest military power and fastest growing economy is still far away from becoming a global superpower due to a lot of different reasons. Although, from 1950's to 2000 and onwards the country's per capita income and literacy rate increased drastically, it still lacks

in many areas which can be preventing it from becoming world's superpower or even come in race of World's biggest powers(Kelly & Garfield, 2012).

- India faces a lot of **challenges** like the environmental problems and has not proven to be effectively resolving them.
- India does have **geographical significance** in Asia, and it occupies a considerably big territory. India does want dominance and influence in Asia, but it does not look possible as the country is surrounded by enemies like China and Pakistan. India has fought battles with both countries in past. Three battles were fought with Pakistan over the issue of Kashmir. In battle with China on 1962 India was defeated badly by the superpower China.
- Because of internal challenges such as poverty, Education unavailability, lagging behind in modern technological advances, environmental crisis, underdeveloped areas, and internal conflicts over race and religion; and external challenges like poor relations with neighboring countries and conflicts over territories, India may not be able to dominate the World in near future. But the struggle of India in becoming part of global politics and international affairs is continued.

Pakistan

The formation of Pakistan as an independent state and then its emergence as a nuclear power has a lot of significance in the Muslim World. Pakistan holds the title of first Islamic nuclear state. But seeing Pakistan as a global power is like a dream. This is so because Pakistan lacks in every area that can contribute to global dominance(Cohen, 2011).

- **Firstly**, our country has been used by great powers to have a check on region. Pakistan has been part of counter terrorism wars but at last lost thousands of lives of its own citizens and soldiers and was gifted with terrorism in return to its sacrifices. Pakistan lost the trust and authority in the region as right from the start it has been house to the proxy wars.
- **Secondly**, internal issues like poor democracy weakened the country greatly. The non-democratic powers have always intervened in the state issues, politics, bureaucracy, and even judiciary.
- **Thirdly**, with our economy which has been deranged so much, there is no sign of global dominance in the near future for us. Pakistan needs to work on every parameter such as economic capability, political stability, and resource management in addition to just gathering weapons and exhausting a large share of budget on amassing nuclear weapons.

All of these factors are sided by a weak foreign policy which has been even more damaged in the recent past. We even couldn't gather the whole Muslim world into a single platform which could have been fruitful for the whole Muslim world and would have been a source of dominance of Muslims in the World. If we have to reclaim our Importance in the World as a nuclear state having one of the World's best militaries, we have to solve all internal and external issues.

AN OVERVIEW OF PAKISTAN'S FOREIGN POLICY

Introduction:

Foreign policy is a part of national policy. It indicates principles and references on which a country make relation with another state for promoting national interest. Foreign policy of a country doesn't remain static, but it changes according to time and circumstances. Pakistan's principles of foreign policy are its ideology and national integration.

Quaid's vision:

In February 1948 a broadcast talk to people of USA, Quaid-e-Azam outlined the following goals of Pakistan foreign policy:

“Our foreign policy is one of friendliness and goodwill towards all the nations of the world. We do not cherish aggressive designs against any country or nation. We believe in the principle of honesty and fair play in National and international dealings and are prepared to make our utmost contribution to promotion of peace and prosperity among the nations of the world. Pakistan will never be found lacking in extending its material and moral support to oppressed and suppressed peoples of the world, and in upholding the principles of the United Nations Charter.”

Basic principles of Foreign Policy of Pakistan;

Pakistan came into being August 1947 and it inherited the legacy of foreign policy from the British India(Muzaffar et al., 2016). However, adjustments was made according to the ideology and objectives of Pakistan movement. Its foreign policy was determined by three factors;

- 1) Security
- 2) Development
- 3) Ideology

Its relationships with religious and superpowers have been fluctuating according to political weather, injecting a permanent feeling of uncertainty in their friendship. However, Pakistan evolved some basic principles of foreign policy which are as under:

- National security
- Economic interest
- Islamic solidarity
- Peaceful coexistence
- Non- alignment
- Bilateralism
- United Nations

Foreign Policy Makers in Pakistan:

- 1) President, prime minister, parliament, and Chief of army staff play a decisive role.
- 2) Foreign office and intelligence give their feedback.
- 3) Public pressure through political parties helps in moulding the foreign policy of Pakistan.

Evaluation of Pakistan's Foreign Policy:

First Phase;

1947-53(exploration and friendship with all)

1953- 62 (Alignment with the west)

Second Phase;

1962- 71 (transition)

1972- 79 (bilateralism and non-alignment)

1980- 90 (Afghanistan and partnership with United States)

Third Phase;

1990- 2001 cold war era and Pakistan dilemmas (Afghanistan problem, Kashmir issue and nuclear sanctions.)

2001- Onward (counter terrorism and economic development along with regional cooperation)

Pakistan and China:

Pak- China relationship beginning in 1950 when Pakistan was among the first countries to enter into official diplomatic relations with the republic of China. China had played a significant role in development, economy, and security of Pakistan. Both countries have placed considerable importance on the maintenance of extremely close and supportive special relationship and the two countries regularly exchange high level visiting result in variety of agreements. The PRC has provided economic military and technical assistance to Pakistan Since the advent of 21st century China has strengthened their relations two bilateral trade military agreement and spotting each other on key success. CPEC is one of the major indications of Pak-China relationship(M. M. Khan & Kasi, 2017).

Pak- United Nations Relations:

The friendship between two countries went through fluctuating levels of friendliness. But Pakistan consistently found themselves on the United States sites of issues faced during the Cold war. Pakistan serves as geographical position for UN states in military bases during the Cold War. These positive relations would fall apart following successful cooperation in fighting the Soviet Union Influence in Central Asia. In reactions to Pakistan new nuclear capacity the UN in 1992 pass the Pressler amendment approving sanctions against Pakistan. The United Nation in Pakistan relation persists of promoting trade and regional Economic Cooperation US also has concerns regarding terrorism, Afghan stability democracy in human rights protection, the ongoing Kashmir problem and Pak-India tension and economic development. Recently US stop military aid to Pakistan which was about US\$2 billion per year(Wasi, 2005).

The Muslim World:

After independence Pakistan made super relationships with other Muslim countries add make a wholehearted bid for leadership of Muslim world. The Ali brothers had sought to project Pakistan as the natural leaders of the Islamic world. Khaliq-uz-Zaman, declared the Pakistan would bring together all Muslim countries to Islamistan – a pan Islamic entity. Pakistan vigorously championed the right of self-determination of Muslim around the world. Pakistan effort the independence movement of Indonesia, Libya, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, Morocco, Azerbaijan, were significant and initially led to close ties between these countries and Pakistan. Pakistan relation with Iran have been strained at times due to sectarian tension. Iran and Saudi Arabia used Pakistan as a battleground for their proxy sectarian war and by the 1990s Pakistan support for Sunni Taliban organization in Afghanistan became a problem for Shia Iran which opposed a Taliban controlled Afghanistan. Tension between Pakistan and Iran intensified in 1998.

Pak-India Relations

Since 1947, Pakistan's relations have been difficult with neighbor India over regional issues. India and Pakistan have fought three conventional wars throughout the 20th century over the issue of [Kashmir](#). There are many sources of tension between the two countries but the issues over terrorism, size disparities and three geostrategic issues: Kashmir, water, and the Siachen Glacier, are the major ones resulting in the attenuated volume of trade and trust deficit. The continuing dispute over the status of Kashmir inflames opinions in both nations and makes friendly relations difficult. In the 1960s, the problems over the Durand Line escalated with Afghanistan which

led to open hostilities in the 1970s. Pakistan is also a member of the Coffee Club to oppose Indian membership in the United Nations Security Council (Muzaffar et al., 2016).

IMPACTS OF GLOBAL POWER DYNAMICS ON PAKISTAN'S FOREIGN POLICY

Dynamics of the world politics revolutionize and get transform greatly as the result of rise and fall of great powers. Global power structure, configuration, player's interests and well beings modify greatly when the key players in the global system either rise and ascend or otherwise get in to fall and descend. These consequences results in the struggle for survival among the key players, old powers start struggling to retain their power while new emerging power struggle to replace the powers of old ones by their authority. As a result, pressure, and tension mounts among old and new players over the preservation or shift of power. There isn't any chance for the countries important for competing powers to have an escape through the power struggle and global alteration. Throbbing and painful tragedies of confrontation, hostilities, conflicts, and battles results mostly when power shift occurred between different civilizations and nation states. For example:

War and Destruction

But after the end of World War 2 US and British for power shift did not adopt the strategy of the war because in the World War 2 British had already pooped and for the power preservation, they don't have the energy to afford one more clash.

The Emergence of Great Power Competition

Different emerging and rising economies have been **triggering the transformation** in global power pattern. The overall global asset structure has been revolutionized as a result of economic growth in many countries especially in the countries of Asia. In past two decades countries like China, Singapore, Japan, South Korea, India, and Malaysia have gained tremendous economic wellbeing and expansion. Quoting the words of the **ParagKanna** from his book "**The futures in Asian**":

"In the 19th century the world was Europeanized, in the 20th century it was Americanized. Now in the 21st century, the world is irreversibly asianized."

In the 21st century, **US and China** are struggling hard to gain the global preeminence. After the end of the Cold War, in the international politics US is playing the role of the **dominant actor**, but on the other hand China worked hard for its **economic growth** and too much extent, it remained successful in its economic expansion that pose threat to US Power of coming to an end. According to their own interest, hidden motives and purposes both powers redefine global power structure, principles and standards which ultimately alters the **power dynamics** in different expanses of the world.

China has been termed as "**The economic powerhouse in Asia.**" According to estimation US power will be overtook by China with in next two decades n terms of economy. These both will be key actors having strong impact and authority on various affairs of the world as per estimation. There is very decisive question in the minds of the realists all the time i.e., **Will the US make an adjustment to China or not. As the realpolitik saying goes:**

"Compromise can be made for the interests, but interests can never be compromised."

Russia's Resurgence in Europe & Middle East:-

Power holders never remain same, or power doesn't remain in the hands of one however in the world politics the rise and fall, transition and shift of the powers is the common phenomenon. History has witnessed ascend and then descend of many great nations Now what the term power includes, the power could include the **strong trade and industry, political, Financial and military influence and authority**. The transitioning of the global power structure of the world from bipolarity to unipolarity and now in recent era to multipolarity ,Russia is

taking the advantage of this situation thereby strengthening its position economically financially and in military perspective too.

Russia is predominating itself in the current world affairs by its intensified involvements. Russia's Foreign policy is now primarily focusing on the incessantly developing **geopolitical and geostrategic atmosphere** in the south Asian region leading to have the strong impact on the whole world politics and global power structure. Today Russia aims to strengthen its position ahead of the international borders. After the **Defense of the Syrian regime, Victorious business enterprise Crimean annexation in 2014 and in the Middle Eastern region its timely contribution and participation**, to regain its reinforcement Russian policy makers are now heading for the South Asia.

Beside of the US pressure Russia and China are strengthening their ties on the **basis of military, economic, trade, industry, and political enlargement**. US sanction against Russia and the trade War between US and China is thought to be circumvented by the growing Russia and China's relationships. Apart from the Russia and China's relationships Russia enjoys good ties with India too. Indian Prime minister, **JawaharLal Nehru** visits to the Russia had flourished the bilateral relationships in military, economic and political aspects between the two countries. Their military association is apparent by the fact that despite of the US sanctions both countries sign the **US \$ 400billion deal of S-400 Missile system**.

Impact on Pakistan

As discussed above Russia's biggest armed hardware importer is **India**. Pakistan deserves to enjoy or benefit of import of the desired armament and military assistance. Russia will be recognized as the regional counter **balancing force** in south Asia for being promoting the **tranquility, peace and stability** in the region if this happens or if Pakistan will enjoy the same position that India is enjoying, this will have a very positive impact on the Pakistan's economy and geostrategic importance. **Russian military dealers** will also get benefitted by this move. As both nations experience the counter terrorism, so both nations should conduct the joint armed exercises on regular basis to get rid of this social evil. For **Moscow Islamabad** will be more worthy as for more than a decade Pakistan army is fighting against the terrorism and the non-state actors(Bowen, 2021).

India: A Self-Styled Regional Hegemony

As US is the big supporter of India this support had led India think that it had a regional hegemony and do whatever it want to do its best example is the **Nullification of Art-370 & 35-A** by India just because of the backing of the US, secondly India is silently establishing its **blue water Navy** and the reason of this rebuilding is to challenge **China's string of pearls policy**. At the international level the India's ascend as the great power is quite obvious after the acknowledgment of the US that it could help the India in maintaining the global peace harmony and the power status. This backing has led India to project its power beyond its border more particularly in the **IOR** which now a day's occupied a **central position in the world politics**(Subramanian & Felman, 2019).

Impact on Pakistan

The rising powers of the India and its backing by US will surely have a strategic impact on its neighboring countries like **China and more particularly Pakistan** also. This impact however won't be able to change the fundamental power balance that exists today but have strong impact on Pakistan. As Pakistan's and India's relationships are the victim of the **distress** since the **partition** of both states, the rise of Indian power will surely pose negative impacts on Pakistan's economy politics and its overall survival. Pakistan is already besieged by the **armed and military strength of India**, i.e., what we see in the Kashmir today making the **future of Kashmir** miserable and uncertain. The only powers that made India to not have a clear attack on Pakistan is the threat of the nuclear exchange or otherwise the state destruction, and the rising powers of the India will never be undermined these both factors. The hegemonic ambitions of the India will surely **destabilize the balance** of power as it is increasing its military assets by increasing its **military ballistic missiles** as well as in its economic means posing the threat of the war(Zeb, 2015).

Saudi-Iran Clash of Interest:-

Saudi Arabia and Iran had a clash of interest for the **regional dominance**. Both the countries are striving to get dominant over the **Middle Eastern and the Asian regions**, and for this they have a continuous tussle between them. They are involved in different clashes over this. Both countries have been locked in an astringent rivalry for the power gain. **Nationalism, race for the regional hegemony, competition for the leadership in the Islamic world, and the sectarian differences** has been further aggravating their rivalry. As both countries support the contrasting sides i.e. there is Sunni majority in the Saudi Arabia while in Iran Shia branch is followed on a large basis(Ali et al., 2020). In the Saudi Iran Power tussle, the **Israel-Palestine** conflict has also been entwined.

Impact on Pakistan

The Saudi Iran tussle and rivalry is not only restricted to the middle east, but it crossed that border and start posing its impact over the **south Asia** where for **Pakistan** it is creating the direct implications in terms of the economy wealth, security, and society. Pakistan has limited Shia population while Sunni population dominates in the region, the tussle between the Saudi and Iran over the power domination had created a very **bottomless**

fracture between the Sunni and Shia population of Pakistan. Iran is supporting the Shiites in the expanse openly after the **1979 rebellion and revolution**, in response to this numerous religious seminars are funded by the **Saudi Arabia in the 1980s**, which focuses on teaching the Islam to people of the Pakistan in a more puritanical version. It had been found that these seminaries were more often involved in prevailing the **sectarian hate** which results in the **radicalization**, and it deepens the roots of division among the Sunni and Shia community of Pakistan. Different sectarian terrorist's outfits are the direct result of the division across the sectarian lines and **religious polarization** in the country due to the Saudi Iran power tussle. In the recent past experience. We the people of Pakistan had faced a serious issue of terrorism and in its contribution, sectarian hate and violence played a vital role to some extent (Ali et al., 2020).

What should be Pakistan's Narrative:-

As the above discussion is based on how the power transition decline and shift is taking place geographically and how it had impacted Pakistan, now Pakistan had to adopt some **defensive measures** as well Pakistan's foreign policy makers had to **reshape the policy** in such a way that balance is created, we have to make our strong ties and bonds with all irrespective of **wrong orbaised favors**, we should have to remain neutral, and had to works for the expansion of our economy and geostrategic position. As far as Saudi Iran conflict over the power is concerned Pakistan has to play its role of a **bridge and peacemaker** in the society. Pakistan should have to balance its relationships between the Iran and Saudi Arabia competently. Pakistan has to take adoption of that kind of policy that will not cause sectarian tension stroked by the Saudi Iran clash to increase.

TRADE WAR BETWEEN CHINA AND US

China and US can be regarded among most powerful countries in every field, so hence are listed under **SUPERPOWERS** list. But both are always having ups and downs in their relations. In 2017, both were among the largest trade partners which can be measured and calculated by their GDP. In 2000, it was observed that China's GDP was tenth of US GPD but when in 2001, China became a part of WTO, its GDP increased about 40% till 2010 from 12% in 2000, almost triple the previous amount. The caused an alarming situation for US. Donald Trump, even before becoming US president was thoroughly criticizing China's trade practices and policies, and hence made several contradictory statements regarding it. In mid of September 2011, he tweeted that China isn't an ally nor their friend for them. The only motive of it is to beat them down and take over their country. The also commented that they cannot allow China to rape their country and are doing what defends them. China was also regarded as greatest thief of the world. From 2011 and till January 2017, both states tried to solve their trade dispute. Many meetings were held, and it seemed that both agreed with the plan to some extent and the global tension is about to perish. But soon in 2018, the tension was again triggered when both of them raised tariff against each other, firstly by the narrow-minded Donald trump, President of US. In March 2018, US imposed 25% tariff on all steel imports except a few countries like Brazil, Argentina and Australia, of course excluding China and also imposed 10% tariff on all aluminum imports as well, again excluding China. China counteracting this behavior, raised the tariff 10% to 25% on about 128 products including fruits, wine, pork, stainless steel, solar panels, and aluminum for most of its trading countries and imposed serious and heavy tax on all Chinese exporting goods.

In addition to these, the US separately imposed 25% tariff on imports from China. The rations of the tariff imposed by China and US was 50 billion dollars to just only 34 billion dollars in July and August in the year 1016. An extra amount of about 16 billion dollars was also added by China Government by the end of July starting of August in 2018. It was clarified that the year 2018- 2019, the worsening relations between both the countries were at peak. China also added an extra amount of 60 billion dollars on US imports and this war remained continued, as there were blockage exchange programs and many more. Both the superpowers are competing well in order to sustain their positions and to overcome one another.

People of US voted for Donald Trump as they believed that he is a man of nerves. He will build stronger reforms and will prove beneficial in terms of foreign policies and relations. But their beliefs got all in vain as he started to go against the superpowers, Russia, China, Iran, Turkey and even India which used to be one of the best of US. China took serious action against it and announced "**Cold War**" against US. According to a report, due to tariff increase by the Chinese Government, US has to suffer a great loss of 51 billion US dollars but on the other had the actions taken by US government failed to impose any negative impact on China's economy. Hence all this dirty politics started by the US Government, came back upon the US itself seriously damaging its sales and even profits.

Due to these structural changes in the power dynamics, its effects are on different regions of the world. It has been said that due to these changes, the world is being irreversibly Asianized.

Global Economic Challenges

There was a great economic setback in 2008 all over the world, after which the global powers especially China started indulging in the global economics to set everyone free from this global depression. Before 2008, the world investment estimated to be about 2 trillion dollars. After a gap of 10 years, this amount had fallen to 20% of the original. Since 2014, it has been in noticed that the global debt is swelling but it relatively stable when

comparing to the GDP. In 2017, the trade was recorded to be the highest with comparison with the last six years.

US-China Relation

When “**NATIONAL SECURITY STRATEGY**” was announced by the notorious US President Donald Trump, many believed that it is against China and claimed it to be the revival of US. Ever since then, US policy is constantly being changing. According to a survey, initially Americans had a good image about Chinese Government and people. It has been estimated that in 2014, 44% of the people had good views about China. This percentage gradually decreased to 38% in 2017. In the Cold War era, the relationships got worse than ever when an American leader was accused of coddling with one of the Beijing leaders, the capital city of China. More over the statement given by US president Donald Trump that “**China is raping us**” also set the relations on fire. In 2017, deficits in US trade started which is about three decades before the trade deficit started in China(CAO Yujue & YUAN Yutong, 2020). This deficit data was considered to be misleading because it was said that China supplies its goods and products to almost all part to the world and the economists are favoring it, and tried to stop the data to be evaluated at multinational firms.

Pakistan and China-US Trade War

Pakistan with its geostrategic position, is it's best to have fruitful relationships with every country especially with the superpowers ever since its establishment. Due to this interactive approach, China launched an economic project CPEC in 2013 of about worth 46 billion dollars which has now reached to 70 billion US Dollars. This project has provided enormous employment to Pakistani people and moreover provides a road route for China to carry out its trade through Pakistani Arabian Sea, again benefiting Pakistan. On the other hand, Pakistan exports a lot of goods to the US. In the year 2003, both countries signed a trading agreement, which increased from 2.8 billion US dollars to 5.8 billion US dollars in 2011. In 2010, top priority of the US for trading was Pakistan. In the year 2019-2020, it was observed that Pakistan export worth was greater than China and on the other hand, China's imports from US were of greater amount than Pakistan. According to many economists, this upheaval between the two superpowers, can prove beneficial for Pakistan's economy. In present circumstances, Pakistan has the golden chance for future investment and introduced bilateral trade attitude with China. Pakistan has become more competitive and have overcome China in many fields like textiles. According to another economist, trade link is getting stronger between Pakistan and US. Pakistan needs more US support than the US needs that of Pakistan's. The bilateral trade between Pakistan and US increased from 2.6 billion dollars to 5.8 billion dollars in 2011. If any hurdle gets in way of Pakistan and US bilateral trade relation, Pakistan economy is going to have serious threats(CAO Yujue & YUAN Yutong, 2020).

FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR INEFFECTIVE FOREIGN POLICY OF PAKISTAN

Background

The term "foreign policy" refers to planned behavior. The most crucial area of research is discovering the factors that influence whether such behavior is successful. This research is attracted by all aspects of foreign policy development and tends to overlook the repercussions of the process. A country's foreign policy is made up of a variety of external and domestic concerns. Geography, economy, culture, history, technology, leadership, and bureaucracy are the most important internal factors.

Elements That Cause Ineffectiveness of Pakistan's Foreign Policy

Foreign policy of each sovereign state evolves throughout time in response to its demands. Nations have interests, and their policies are focused only on the benefits they may get, not on buddies or foes. Any neighboring state can be useful, depending on the capacity to establish long-term border peace goals. Pakistan-Afghanistan relations are an excellent illustration of this since the country is unable to define its foreign policy outside the Cold War limits. India's centered foreign policy has hampered Pakistan's foreign strategy. Except for China, Pakistan has strong ties with its neighbors. Tensions between Pakistan and India shifted to the western border after the Kargil conflict concluded in 1999, but Pakistan's proxy war with another country, Afghanistan, continued. Pakistan's foreign policy has failed miserably as a result of these two factors. Other considerations include worldwide determination to terminate the Taliban-led conflict that has shattered our country on a global and regional scale. Pakistan has also failed because of common linguistic, ethnic, and cultural realities with Afghanistan, while our adversary, India, has utilized deception and stepped in with a big economic promise for the Afghan state's welfare. Because of all these factors, Pakistan's strategy in Afghanistan has failed to some extent. Pakistan's foreign policy with Iran has had certain successes, but it has also failed in key areas, such as serious issues in expanding ties with Iran at a time when Pakistan must balance its relationship with Saudi Arabia. Saudi Arabia's regional proxy conflicts make it more difficult for Pakistan and Iran to express their sentiments and enhance their foreign policies. Another issue is that as Pakistan's relations with Iran improve the country's relations with Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates deteriorate. As a result, the foreign policies of both India and Pakistan have failed. Many issues, including the Kargil conflict, Kashmir, Junagarh, the 1965 and 1971 conflicts, water disputes, and the Bengal refugee crisis, can never be addressed since they are all crucial (1949). Pakistan's foreign strategy is based on reducing the threat from India while maintaining the status quo in Kashmir. Three wars have previously erupted between Pakistan and India over this topic. Pakistan's ties to

the rest of the Muslim world may be traced back to ancient times. Due to a lack of foreign policy leadership, Pakistan's connections with Islamic countries are similarly poor. Pakistan's long-term national interest cannot be served by its isolation in the region.

The following problems have also contributed to Pakistan's failure in foreign policy:

Regional Factors

The geostrategic relevance of Pakistan aids policymakers in developing a well-balanced foreign strategy. Pakistan and China have strong bilateral ties, and China has consistently backed Pakistan in tough times. China is seen as a danger to India's economic objectives and regional hegemonic aspirations. Apart from these advantages, India, as Pakistan's archenemy, is continually trying to sabotage Pakistan's foreign policy. America is likewise attempting to do so, as China is Pakistan's closest ally and a rising economic and military superpower (Zeb, 2015).

Weak Economic Situation

As a result of its weak economic situation, Pakistan has maintained tight ties with wealthier nations such as the United States and international organizations such as the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank, often at a cost. These organizations have interfered with the lending nations' monitoring, social, and political policies. Pakistan is one of the world's most financed countries, with loans from the US, China, Saudi Arabia, the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, and others (Z. Iqbal, 2011).

Kashmir Issue

Pakistan's foreign policy agenda has been dominated by the Kashmir problem. Pakistan regards Kashmir as its jugular vein, and India as the aggressor in the heinous enslavement of Kashmir. Its relations with India, the United States, China, and Russia, as well as the Muslim world, have been harmed by the Kashmir problem. In the 1950s, Pakistan was forced to identify with the American Block in order to maintain its security through military aid and economic support. Both India and Pakistan have been involved in three wars and various conflicts, the most recent of which being the Kargil conflict in 1999 (Nawaz, 2018).

Corruption

Corruption has an influence on inequality, general investment, crime, official growth, foreign trade and aid, the shadow economy, and foreign direct investment. The corruption model shows how corruption causes poverty by modifying the governance factors that cause poverty (Javaid, 2010).

Terrorism

The use of immoral violence against individuals for political gain is classified as terrorism. Unlawful use of force against people or property for personal or political gain. Terrorism's goal is to get as much attention as possible using the media. Because Pakistan has a higher terrorist rate than the rest of the globe, terrorism has a significant impact on Pakistani foreign policy. The New Zealand cricket team has declined to play in Pakistan due to security concerns. Terrorism has an influence on policy since it jeopardizes Pakistan's economic goals (Malik et al., 2019).

Money Laundering

Money laundering is another policy-related phenomenon. Money laundering is sometimes thought of as a way for criminals to conceal their illegal origins. Throughout this strategy, the crooks earn without jeopardizing their sources. The United Nations and other international organizations are working hard to bring attention to this delicate subject, which is causing foreign policy failure. Terrorists benefit because their crimes are easy to carry out, and the general population is robbed of lawful money and rights as a result. Surfing is one of the most prevalent types. To escape discovery, crooks break their big sums of money into little chunks throughout this process (Ahmed et al., 2015).

Poor Governance

There is a link between those who dominate and those who are controlled as a result of decisions made. Corruption, portrayal, and unjust policies are all hallmarks of bad government. Lack of accountability and dishonesty on the part of those in positions of authority, as well as corruption, are all factors that contribute to poor governance. Foreign policy failure is caused by poor governance. Furthermore, the administration is to blame for a lackluster foreign policy due to a slew of financial, political, and legal issues. Pakistan seldom fails to implement foreign policy due to political and sociological contrasts with other countries (A. Iqbal, 2015).

RECOMMENDATIONS TO MAKE FOREIGN POLICY OF PAKISTAN EFFECTIVE IN LIGHT OF GLOBAL POWER DYNAMICS

1. By Promoting International Trade

It is the activity of selling and buying goods among countries. It exposes countries to goods which they are not able to produce by using their own resources. The foreign policy of Pakistan can be made effective by promoting international trade. When Pakistan will utilize its resources (like labours, techniques etc.), it would be able to make list of goods in accordance with its resources at a more rapid rate with low cost. When these goods are exported, it results in the development of economy. Consequently, a strong economy results in a more effective foreign policy due to benefit from currency exchange. Further by promoting trade activities with other countries, it results in establishment of good relations with them. As a result, we will have support of more

countries, friendly relations will be developed, and Pakistan will be regarded as a peaceful country. It will have a positive impact on Pakistan's economy (Shafi et al., 2020).

2. Balanced Foreign Policy

Another way of making foreign policy effective is the formation of balanced foreign policy. Balanced foreign policy means making a foreign policy having points with ability to impress other countries. The foreign policy should not be made just in accordance with a view of having benefits and advantages. Rather our foreign policy should constitute such points that if a country doesn't like one point, it finds its benefits in another. We should not make foreign policy by having a thought of enemies and friends in our mind. Rather we should make it effective by making it balanced by including the points that they make attention seeker of other countries. As a result, when other countries find their advantage in the points of our foreign policy they will make agreements with us, resulting in good relations between the countries. Consequently, Pakistan will be recognized as good friend, peaceful country. Further we will have more support of global powers resulting in positive impact on our foreign policy (Rai, 2020).

3. By Promoting Tourism

We can make foreign policy effective by promoting tourism in Pakistan. We should promote tourism and allow tourists to come to Pakistan. They will come and explore more about Pakistan. They will know about Pakistani land, its culture, its people, and its beauty. Most importantly they will come to know how peaceful country Pakistan is! So, when they will go back to their countries and move around the world, they will have positive feedback regarding Pakistan. They will praise Pakistan. They will testify of the fact that Pakistan is a peace loving country. As a result when global powers encounter more information about regions, beauty, mineral, resources etc. in Pakistan, their interest will rise in Pakistan. They will tend to develop more friendly relations with Pakistan (J. Khan et al., 2022). This will have a good and positive impact on foreign policy of Pakistan.

4. Establishing Good Relations with Muslim Countries and Uniting Muslim Ummah

Pakistan has always tried hard for establishing good relations with Muslim countries and unity of Muslim world. This is because unity of Muslim is a source of protection and benefit for Pakistan as well as all Muslim countries. Our Holy Prophet (S.A.W) also worked for this purpose for ultimate strength and development of Muslims. It can be achieved by helping Muslim brothers and Muslim countries during some bad situations like economic problems, defence problems, war etc. There are various events where Pakistan worked for Muslim world unity. For example, Pakistan supported Arab alliance in 1973 during Arab-Israel war. Pakistan is a member of OIC and has performed major role in OIC to make its foreign policy effective. Helping Muslim countries creates a sense of harmony between Muslim worlds which directly affects our foreign policy (I. Khan, 2012).

5. Measures to Eradicate Terrorism and Curb Money Laundering

Another important task to be performed is to work for eradicating terrorism and money laundering from the country. These activities have a bad impact on other countries resulting in bad relations with them. As a result, we have an ineffective foreign policy. **Financial action task force (FATF)** is the international organisation that works for eradicating these practices. It has listed Pakistan under **grey list** meaning that Pakistan is a country that supports terrorism financing. This has a severely bad effect on foreign policy of Pakistan. So, government should take immediate measures to remove Pakistan from grey list (Qureshi, 2017).

6. Establishment of Good Governance

Good governance is the process in which all the processes in public institutions all well performed without any dishonesty, inequality, corruption, and fundamental rights are fulfilled. Unfortunately, Pakistan is facing the problem of bad governance which is hampering the process of Pakistan's development. It can be turned into good governance by taking the following measure:

- Disunion of governmental and non-governmental resources
- Government should mediate and continue the developmental programmes of previous governments
- Rural areas must be developed
- Laws and organizations should be made to eradicate corruption and other social evils
- Workers should be given their deserving wages

These above steps result in good governance that decides the national services among the people. It provides equal opportunities for social and economic development. Consequently, economic development results in a good foreign policy (Ismail & Rizvi, 2000)

Conclusion

As the above discussion is based on how the world power alters and shift is taking place geographically and how it had impacted Pakistan, now Pakistan has to adopt some defensive measures as well Pakistan's foreign policy makers have to reshape the policy in such a way that balance is created, we have to make our strong ties and bonds with all irrespective of wrong or biased favors, we should have to remain neutral, and have to work for the expansion of our economy and geostrategic position. As far as Saudi Iran conflict over the power is concerned Pakistan has to play its role of a bridge and peacemaker in the society. Pakistan should have to balance its relationships between the Iran and Saudi Arabia competently. Pakistan has to take adoption of that kind of policy that will not cause sectarian tension stroked by the Saudi Iran clash to increase. Pakistan is doing its best to act in accordance with the desired advice being given in the form of almost 27/28 point a list by FATF, out of which 20 points have been satisfactory. It is trying to get the diplomatic nod of the global influential players and has succeeded in winning the diplomatic nod of the Malaysia and Turkey. Pakistan had failed the FATF because FATF wanted to secure place in Pakistan's foreign policy. UK has changed its travel advisory towards Pakistan followed by United States of America. Pakistan had made serious efforts to create soft image in the eyes of the world. Terrorism causes problems for Pakistan as it tarnished respectful image of Pakistan, but it has been controlled. It is Pakistan's economy that compels it not to strike a balanced international approach in major dynamics of global power. To avoid problems in Pakistan foreign policy, Pakistan has adopted harsh and aggressive measures in its economic sphere to boost up its Economic strength. For this purpose, it signed the agreement of CPEC with China to avail Chinese markets. Its main purpose was to meet unemployment, energy shortage and infrastructure in Pakistan. KSAs investment in Pakistan is remarkable. Pakistan is doing best to raise its economy and play its role in world affairs. Pakistan is facing the changing to its foreign policy, in its security and diplomatic posture and is, if to say, fighting well with all of them. Its balanced approach between US and China triggers the role of mediator between KSA and Iran. Pakistan has done efforts to reduce terrorism and tourism to get fruits. Above all, Pakistan tackled all the problems in its foreign policy to a considerable extent.

References

- Ahmed, R., Siddiqui, K., & Choudhry, D. (2015). Money Laundering In Pakistan. *International Journal of Marketing and Technology*, 3(9), 247–276.
- Ali, A., Ahmad, M., & Nawaz, A. (2020). Saudi Iranian Rivalry: The Struggle for Power and Influence in the Middle East. *Pakistan Social Sciences Review*, 4(III), 587–598. [https://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2020\(4-iii\)42](https://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2020(4-iii)42)
- Almotairi, S. G. (2021). China's Emergence As a Potential Superpower and the World Order. *Margalla Papers*, 25(2), 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.54690/margallapapers.25.2.89>
- Bowen, A. S. (2021). *Russian Arms Sales and Defense Industry*. <https://crsreports.congress.gov>
- CAO Yujue, & YUAN Yutong. (2020). The Trend of U.S.-China Relations: Is a Conflict Between the United States and China Inevitable? *International Relations and Diplomacy*, 8(7), 290–297. <https://doi.org/10.17265/2328-2134/2020.07.002>
- Cohen, S. P. (2011). FOREIGN POLICY at Brookings: The Future of Pakistan. In *The brookings institution*. https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/01_pakistan_cohen.pdf
- Dyner, A. M. (2012). The Future of Russia: Modernization or Decline? *The Polish Quarterly of International Affairs*, 21(3), 116.
- Iqbal, A. (2015). Governance Issues in Pakistan and Their Impact on Income Inequality. *IBT Journal of Business Studies*, 11(2), 213–228. <https://doi.org/10.46745/ilma.jbs.2015.11.02.16>
- Iqbal, Z. (2011). Pakistan's Economic Challenges and Environmental Issues. *SBP Research Bulletin*, 7(1), 68–85.
- Ismail, Z. H., & Rizvi, S. (2000). *SOME ISSUES OF GOVERNANCE IN PAKISTAN*. March, 1–23.
- Javaid, U. (2010). Corruption and Its Deep Impact on Good Governance in Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 48(1), 123–134. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41762417>
- KARATAŞ, İ. (2021). The United States: Is It Still a Superpower? *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Vizyoner Dergisi*, 12(30), 677–688. <https://doi.org/10.21076/vizyoner.810814>
- Kelly, E. L., & Garfield, S. (2012). *India*.
- Khan, I. (2012). Pakistan's strategic culture and foreign policy making: A study of Pakistan's post 9/11 Afghan policy change. In *Pakistan's Strategic Culture and Foreign Policy Making: A Study of Pakistan's Post 9/11 Afghan Policy Change* (1st ed.). Nova Science Publishers.
- Khan, J., Ali, A., Zada, M., Saeed, I., & Zada, S. (2022). *Pakistan's Tourism Industry: Full of potential, but still lagging behind*. 1–11.
- Khan, M. K., & Wei, L. (2016). When friends turned into enemies: The role of the national state vs. Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) in the war against terrorism in Pakistan. *Korean Journal of Defense Analysis*, 28(4), 597–626.

- Khan, M. M., & Kasi, M. (2017). Pakistan-China relations: Developments in economic and security areas in the 21st century. *Strategic Studies*, 37(3), 55–74. <http://www.popularsocialscience.com/2013/11/06/neorealism-in-international->
- Malik, Z. U. A., He, Z., & Rafay, M. (2019). War on Terrorism in Pakistan: Challenges and Strategic Steps. *Vestnik RUDN. International Relations*, 19(4), 625–631. <https://doi.org/10.22363/2313-0660-2019-19-4-625-631>
- Muzaffar, M., Yaseen, Z., & Ishfaq, U. (2016). Pakistan's Foreign Policy: Initial Perspectives and Stages. *Global Regional Review*, 1(1), 61–74. [https://doi.org/10.31703/grr.2016\(i-i\).05](https://doi.org/10.31703/grr.2016(i-i).05)
- Nawaz, A. (2018). AN APPRAISAL OF KASHMIR CONFLICT. *International Journal of Asian History, Culture and Tradition*, 5(4), 46–49.
- Potter, S. J. (2007). Empire, Cultures and Identities in Nineteenth- and Twentieth-Century Britain. *History Compass* 5/1, 5(1), 51–71.
- Qureshi, W. A. (2017). An overview of money laundering in Pakistan and worldwide: Causes, methods, and socioeconomic effects. *University of Bologna Law Review*, 2(2), 300–345. <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.2531-6133/7816>
- Rai, F. (2020). Neutrality-cum-Balancing: Understanding Pakistan's Foreign and Diplomatic Policy in the MENA Region. *Journal of Current Affairs*, 4(1&2), 117–142.
- Shafi, M., Liu, J., & Ren, W. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on micro, small, and medium-sized Enterprises operating in Pakistan. *Research in Globalization*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resglo.2020.100018>
- Subramanian, A., & Felman, J. (2019). India's Great Slowdown: What Happened? What's the Way Out? In *CID Faculty Working Paper No. 370* (Issue Center for International Development).
- Victoria, A. (2006). *The New 21st Century World Order* (Issue December). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11871.41120>
- Wasi, N. (2005). Pakistan and the United Nations. *Source: Pakistan Horizon*, 58(3), 57–64. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41392206> <http://about.jstor.org/terms>
- White, O., & Heath, E. (2017). Introduction: The French Empire and the history of economic life. *French Politics, Culture and Society*, 35(2), 76–88. <https://doi.org/10.3167/fpcs.2017.350207>
- Zeb, R. (2015). PAKISTAN-CHINA RELATIONS: WHERE THEY GO FROM HERE? *REVESCO Revista de Estudios Cooperativos*, 121(March 2014), 7–32. <https://doi.org/10.5209/rev>

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